

Spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III) with *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine from succinate media

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Abstract : Spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III) with *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine in xylene from succinate medium was carried out. Ruthenium(III) was extracted quantitatively with 10 ml of 1×10^{-4} M reagent concentration in xylene from 0.001 M sodium succinate concentration in 25 ml aqueous phase with 2% sodium chloride solution and estimated spectrophotometrically with pyridine-2-thiol at 620 nm. The effect of metal ions, acid, reagent concentrations and various foreign ions have been investigated. The method affords quantitative binary separation of ruthenium(III) and is applicable to the analysis of synthetic mixtures and alloys. The method is highly selective, simple and reproducible. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of ruthenium(III)*N*-decylpyridine-4-amine complex is (1.2×10^5 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and (0.0078 μg cm⁻²), respectively which indicates the applicability of the method.

Keywords : Ruthenium(III), *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine, solvent extraction, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

The abundance of ruthenium in the earth's crust is about 0.001%. It is used as a hardening agent for palladium and platinum. Small amounts of this element greatly increase the corrosion of titanium. It is a versatile catalyst, used in the selective reduction of carbonyl groups in organic compounds by hydrogen and the removal of hydrogen sulfide from oil refining and other processes¹. Solvent extraction of noble metals has been widely employed in chemistry and industry for many years. This technique has been used for the separation of platinum metals²⁻⁴. These noble metals are recovered from a wide variety of sources because they can cause metallurgical problems of widely differing natures. The aqueous chemistry of these metals is extremely complex. The most prominent feature of their chemistry is the great tendency of the metals to form chlorocomplexes in chloride media. In addition, the stabilities of the chlorocomplexes are widely different. In general, two effects are used to achieve separation by anion exchange⁵ : (1) the differing stabilities of chlorocomplex anions and (2) differences in structure, charge, and size among different chlorocomplexes. The first effect is most useful in separating the noble

metals from base metals. In moderately weak chloride medium most base metals are present in solution in the cationic forms where as the noble metal chlorocomplexes are stable (or inert to substitution) at fairly low chloride concentrations. The second effect is useful in achieving both group and individual noble metal separations. Solvent extraction by high molecular weight amines (HMWA) has become increasingly popular in recent years for studying metal complexes. These are known as liquid anion exchangers which uniquely combine some of the advantages of liquid-liquid extraction and ion exchange. It was further observed that the acid binding properties of high molecular weight amines depends on the fact that acid salts of these bases are essentially insoluble in water while they are readily soluble in hydrocarbon solvent⁶.

Experimental

Synthesis of N-decylpyridine-4-amine :

Step-1 :

N-Decylpyridine-4-amine was synthesized using equimolar proportion of *N*-decylaldehyde and 4-aminopyridine in 20 ml DCM and 0.1 mg of metal catalyst and was refluxed for 3-4 h. The product was sepa-

rated and recrystallized from hot ethanol as white shiny needles (m.p. 68–70 °C).

Step-2 :

Product of step-1 (Schiff base) is reduced by NaBH₄ by taking equimolar amounts of Schiff base and NaBH₄ in absolute methanol and refluxed for 30 min, product was separated and recrystallized from hot ethanol (m.p. 245 °C).

The purity of compound was monitored using ¹H NMR, FT-IR and mass spectra. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 0.87 (3H, t, -CH₃), 1.87 (2H, d, -CH₂), 1.26 (2H, d, -CH₂), 3.4 (2H, s, -CH₂), 4.1 (1H, s, -NH), 6.5 (2H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, aromatic protons), 8.2 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, aromatic protons); IR (cm⁻¹) : 2922 (=C-H), 1331 (C-N), 1513–1640 (C=C), 3429 (N-H); Mass *m/e* : 236 (100.0%) (M⁺).

Chemicals :

N-Decylpyridine-4-amine (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) was used as an extractant; its solution was prepared in xylene. A stock solution of ruthenium(III) was prepared by dissolving 1 g of ruthenium chloride hydrate (S. D. Fine, India) in dilute analytical reagent grade hydrochloric acid (1 mol/dm³) and diluting to 100 ml with distilled water and further standardized gravimetrically¹⁰. A working solution 100 µg ml⁻¹ of ruthenium(III) was prepared from it by diluting the stock solution with distilled water. Other standard solutions of different metal ions used to study the effect of foreign ions were prepared by dissolving weighed quantities of respective salts in double distilled water or dilute hydrochloric acid solution. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double distilled water was invariably used throughout the measurements. Considering the

importance of ruthenium(III), an attempt has been made to investigate the applicability of solvent extraction method using high molecular weight amines as a part of continuation of our earlier studies.

Instruments :

A Jasco V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell was used for absorbance measurements, pH measurements were carried out with Systronics digital pH Meter Model No. 802.

General procedure :

An aqueous solution containing 100 µg of ruthenium(III) was mixed with sufficient quantity of sodium succinate (0.033 g) to make its concentration 0.005 M in total volume of 25 ml of the metal solution, then pH was adjusted in the range 6–10 using dilute hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide, The solution was transferred in to a 125 ml separating funnel and shaken with 10 ml *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine in xylene for 15–60 s. After equilibration, the mixture was allowed to separate and the metal ion was stripped from the organic phase with two 10 ml portions of 2% sodium chloride solution. The extract was evaporated to moist dryness. The residue was dissolved in 10 ml of pyrimidine-2-thiol solution and the absorbance of brownish colored solution was measured at 620 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and discussion

Ruthenium(III) reacts with extractant and forms 1 : 1 metal-ligand complex. The complex has maximum absorption at 620 nm. The molar absorptivity (1.2 × 10⁵ L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and Sandell's sensitivity (0.0078 µg cm⁻²), of the complex suggest that trace and ultra trace level quantities of ruthenium can be quantified with required accuracy and precision. The influence of various factors like pH, reagent concentration, choice of solvent and effect of foreign ions on the extraction efficiency of ruthenium(III) has been studied while optimizing the conditions for the selective and rapid extraction at trace level quantities.

The spectral properties of the Ru-*N*-decylpyridine-4-amine :

The absorption spectra of the Ru-*N*-decylpyridine-4-amine complexes were measured against a reagent blank, that of the reagent treated in a similar manner against a

pyrimidine-2-thiol. The Ru-*N*-decylpyridine-4-amine complex has brown color and one strong absorbance peak at 620 nm. Therefore all the measurements have performed at 620 nm.

Extraction as a function of pH :

Ruthenium(III) was extracted in the pH range 6–10 in the presence of weak organic acids such as sodium salts of malonic (0.025 *M*) and succinic acid (0.001 *M*). Quantitative extraction of ruthenium(III) was observed in the pH range 6–10 from sodium succinate media. There was incomplete extraction of ruthenium(III) from sodium malonate (75%) while no extraction was observed from sodium oxalate media (Fig. 1). Out of different organic acids such as sodium salt of salicylic acid, tartaric acid, acetic acid, in tartaric acid, acetic acid and mineral acid media very less extraction was found. This shows that the equilibrium in the pH range 6–10 is favourable for the formation of ion pair complex from sodium succinate media. Hence sodium salt of succinate was used for further studies.

Fig. 1. Extraction of ruthenium(III) with 1×10^{-4} *M* *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine in xylene as a function of pH.

Effect of N-decylpyridine-4-amine concentration :

In order to optimize the conditions for the extraction of ruthenium(III), solutions of *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine

with varying concentrations 1×10^{-5} – 1×10^{-1} were employed at constant sodium succinate concentration. It was found that 1×10^{-5} *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine was sufficient for quantitative extraction of 100 μ g ruthenium(III) from 0.001 *M* sodium succinate, but in recommended procedure 1×10^{-4} *M* concentration of *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine in xylene was used to ensure the complete extraction of metal ion. There was no adverse effect if one can use excess of extractant. However, a decrease in concentration of extractant resulted in lower distribution ratio, [D] for ruthenium(III).

Fig. 2. Structure of *N*-*n*-decylaminopyridine.

Effect of weak organic acid concentration :

The study of the chlorocomplexes of the platinum group metals clearly indicates that the strength of interaction with ion exchangers is highly dependent on the charge of the complex. Therefore, the ruthenium(III) chlorocomplex is poorly extracted which is due to the charge of the complex as well as its labile character towards aquation. Hence, it is worthwhile to develop the solvent extraction procedure in weak organic acid media. One of the distinct advantage of the malonate media is the facility of controlling the concentration of complexing ligand, the ease of adjustment of pH and wide differences in pH at which various metal ions form anionic complexes. It is observed that succinate media offers better phase separation possibly due to high stability of metal organic acid complex. The extraction of ruthenium(III) was carried out in the pH range 6–10 with 1×10^{-4} *M* *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine in xylene in the presence of varying concentration of sodium malonate, sodium salicylate, sodium succinate and sodium oxalate as weak acid media and also in mineral acid media. The extraction of ion-pair complex of ruthenium(III) was found to be quantitative at 0.001 *M* sodium succinate concentration. With increased concentration of sodium succinate there is decrease in the extraction of ruthenium(III). The decrease in the extraction at high acid concentration is presumably due to preferential formation of the succinate of the *N*-decylpyridine-4-

amine. Therefore, a 0.001 *M* concentration of sodium succinate was used throughout this work. While extraction was found to be incomplete in mineral acid, and no extraction from sodium oxalate media.

Effect of diluents :

The extraction was performed from succinate medium using 1×10^{-4} *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine in various solvents as diluents. It was found that ligand solution in carbontetrachloride, chloroform, toluene, benzene, xylene shows quantitative extraction of ruthenium(III). The extraction of ruthenium(III) was found to be incomplete in isobutylmethylketone, isoamylalcohol, *n*-butanol. Xylene is recommended for further extraction procedure as it is a nonpolar solvent. In nonpolar solvent in absence of repulsive forces, the extraction is maximum while in polar solvent the association of cationic species with extraction is minimum, xylene doesn't form emulsion and offers better phase separation.

Effect of stripping agent :

Stripping is the reverse of extraction, so it should be promoted by those factors that affect extraction negatively, such as acidic and salt media. Stripping is removal of the extracted solute from the organic phase for further analysis. The conditions employed depends on the nature of metal ion and the particular extraction system and are such that they promote the reversal of extraction. The stripping of ruthenium(III) is quantitative with 2% sodium chloride solution. The stripping was found to be incomplete with nitric acid (60%), sulphuric acid (40%) where as ruthenium(III) was not stripped with, sodium hydroxide and water.

Effect of aqueous to organic volume ratio :

The results of contacting different volume ratios of organic to aqueous phase have been studied and a preferred aqueous/organic (A/O) phase ratio in this study was found to be 5 : 1 or less. This is evident from the sharp increase in the separation efficiency as well as the distribution ratio of ruthenium(III) when phase ratio (A/O) changed from 20 : 1 to 5 : 1. This may simply be due to the unavailability of reagent for metal extraction and so a crowding effect occurs at low phase ratio. However, in the recommended procedure the phase ratio is maintained as 2.5 : 1 so as to avoid the large consumption of sodium succinate.

Effect of time on extraction :

The effect of time was observed for a period of 5 s to 30 min (handshaking). The extraction was found quantitative over the periods longer than 10 s. But to ensure the complete extraction of ruthenium(III) 1 min time was recommended. However, a prolonged shaking period doesn't have any adverse effect on the extraction.

Loading capacity of N-decylpyridine-4-amine :

The loading capacity of the extractant was determined by the repeated contact of organic phase with a fresh feed solution of the metal of same concentration. For a 10 ml (1×10^{-4} *M*) solution of *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine in xylene at 0.001 *M* sodium succinate concentration and a A/O of 2.5 : 1, the maximum loading capacity for ruthenium(III) was found to be 6.5 mg.

Effect of various foreign ions :

Ruthenium(III) was extracted in the presence of a large number of foreign cations and anions (Table 1). The tolerance limit was set out as the amount of the foreign ion that could be present to give an error less than $\pm 2\%$ recovery of ruthenium(III). The reproducibility of ruthenium(III) extraction was investigated from six replicate measurements. After the phase separation, the organic phase was stripped with two 10 ml portions of 2% sodium chloride solution. The residue was dissolved in 10 ml of pyrimidine-2-thiol solution and ruthenium(III) was determined spectrophotometrically by pyrimidine-2-thiol⁷⁻⁹.

Applications :

Binary separation of ruthenium(III) from Pd^{II}, Rh^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Au^{III}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III} :

The method allowed separation and determination of ruthenium(III) from a binary mixture containing Pd^{II}, Rh^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Au^{III}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III}. In a typical experiment, solution containing 100 μg of ruthenium(III) was taken and known amounts of other metals were added, ruthenium(III) was estimated spectrophotometrically. The recovery of ruthenium(III) and that of added ions was 99.5% and results are reported in Table 2.

Analysis of synthetic mixtures :

The separation of ruthenium(III) from other platinum group metals (platinum, rhodium, palladium and gold) and base metals, there is quantitative extraction of Pd^{II},

Table 1. Effect of foreign ions on the extraction of ruthenium(III)

Foreign ion	Added as	Tolerance limit (mg)	Foreign ion	Added as	Tolerance limit (mg)
Rh ^{III}	RhCl ₃ .H ₂ O	2	Sr ^{II}	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	15
Pt ^{IV}	H ₂ PtCl ₆	2	Pb ^{II}	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	15
Au ^{III}	HAuCl ₄	3	Ti ^{IV}	K ₂ .TiF ₆ .H ₂ O	10
Pd ^{II}	PdCl ₂ .H ₂ O	2	U ^{VI}	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	15
Cr ^{III}	CrCl ₃	15	Bi ^{III}	Bi(NO ₃) ₃ .5H ₂ O	5
Mn ^{II}	MnCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	20	Iodide	Iodide	25
Co ^{II}	CoCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	15	Fluoride	Fluoride	25
Ni ^{II}	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	20	Bromide	Bromide	20
Cu ^{II}	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	25	Oxalate	Oxalate	25
Fe ^{III}	NH ₄ Fe(SO ₄) ₂ .12H ₂ O	15	Nitrate	Nitrate	25
Fe ^{II}	FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	20	Thiourea	Thiourea	20
Zn ^{II}	ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	15	Succinate	Succinate	25
Hg ^{II}	HgCl ₂	20	Chloride	Chloride	25
Mg ^{II}	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	25	EDTA	EDTA	50
Sn ^{II}	SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	15	Tartarate	Tartarate	50

Table 2. Separation and determination of ruthenium(III) from binary mixtures

Metal ion	Amount taken (µg)	Average (%) Recovery*	Reference number
Ru ^{III}	100	99.8	9
Rh ^{II}	100	99.9	
Ru ^{III}	100	99.7	9
Pt ^{IV}	300	99.8	
Ru ^{III}	100	99.8	9
Au ^{III}	300	99.9	
Ru ^{III}	100	99.9	9
Pd ^{II}	15000	99.7	
Ru ^{III}	100	99.7	10
Cu ^{II}	15000	99.8	
Ru ^{III}	100	99.8	10
Co ^{II}	10000	99.7	
Ru ^{III}	100	99.8	10
Ni ^{II}	10000	99.8	
Ru ^{III}	100	99.9	10
Fe ^{III}	10000	99.7	

Pt^{IV} and Au^{III} but the co-extracted metal ions cannot be back stripped by 2% sodium chloride solution thus, the reagent *N*-decylpyridine-4-amine is made selective towards ruthenium(III) by taking the advantage of strippent used (Table 3).

Analysis of alloys :

The proposed method is applicable for the determina-

Table 3. Analysis of synthetic mixture

Composition (µg)	Ruthenium(III) found (µg)	Mean	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)
Ru, 100; Pt ^b , 500; Pd, 200	199.8	199.84	99.94	0.06
Ru, 100; Pt ^b , 500; Rh ^a , 500	199.8	199.82	99.92	0.08
Ru, 500; Au, 100; Pt ^b , 200	199.9	199.82	99.94	0.07
Ru, 100; Pt ^b , 500; Pd, 500; Au, 500	199.9	199.82	99.92	0.06
Ru, 100; Pt ^b , 500; Rh ^a , 500; Au, 500	199.9	199.86	99.96	0.07

Table-3 (contd.)

Ru, 100; Fe, 1000;	199.9	199.80	99.92	0.07
Cu, 1000; Ni, 500	199.9			
	199.8			
	199.7			
	199.7			

^aMasked with tartarate. ^bMasked with oxalate.

tion of ruthenium(III) content in the thermocouple wire and alloy. Dissolution of sample is carried out by using literature method^{11,12}. To ascertain the selectivity of the reagent, the proposed method was successfully used in the determination of ruthenium(III) in alloys. The synthetic mixtures were prepared corresponding to the composition of alloy. The results of the analysis are reported in Table 4. The average recovery of ruthenium(III) was 99.5%.

Table 4. Analysis of synthetic mixtures corresponding to alloy

Alloys	Composition (%)	Amount of ruthenium(III) found by proposed method ^a (%)	RSD ^b (%)
Palladium-ruthenium alloy	Ru 5, 87; Pt 95	4.8	0.2
Jewelry alloy	Ru, 4; Pd 95; Rh 1	3.9	0.2

^aAverage of five determinations.

^bRSD (%) = (Standard Amount – Amount found/Standard amount) × 100.

Conclusions

In the present work, a simple, sensitive, inexpensive and selective method was developed for the extraction and separation of ruthenium(III) from binary mixtures, synthetic mixtures and alloys. The proposed method has several remarkable analytical characteristics :

(i) It is free from interference from the large number of diverse ions which are associated with ruthenium(III) in its natural occurrence.

(ii) The important features of this method are that low reagent concentration is required for complete extraction of ruthenium(III) and also time required to establish equilibrium is very short (30 s).

(iii) The method is very simple, selective and reproducible having required Sandell's sensitivity.

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